

1 - IN-HABIT Data Platform

Solution developed by the IN-HABIT consortium partners

Value Proposition

Using citizen science to study how environmental factors impact health and well-being this comprehensive digital platform provides an adaptable and scalable infrastructure. The modular structure of this flexible architecture was designed with long-term use in mind and supports the integration of real time and historic data from multiple data sources into personalized dashboards for decision makers and researchers. Additionally, by supporting open standards (such as FIWARE and NGS-LD) it allows for easier discovery, access, and sharing of data thereby maximizing its potential reuse for both research and public policy.

Key Activities

- **Development and management of the platform:** The continuous development and management of the platform.
- **Data Collection and Integration:** Collecting and integrating a variety of data on a continuous basis using different methods.
- **Data Visualization and Analysis:** Interpreting and monitoring the relevant qualitative and quantitative parameters by processing and displaying the data collected.
- **Deploying sensor networks:** These are physical devices including street sensors and cameras which will collect data.

Cost Structure

- **Infrastructure and equipment:** The cost of developing apps, cloud maintenance, and purchasing hardware (sensors and cameras)
- **Sensor network operations:** The costs for deploying and maintaining the devices that measure air quality, noise, temperature, and traffic flow
- **Personnel:** The salaries of the teams working on the project
- **Communication:** Budget for marketing materials, website management, and social media campaigns.

Revenue Streams

- **This platform generates potential revenue streams from subscription fees for accessing the platform.**

Partnerships

- **Pilot City Leads:** The individuals and/or organizations that support the local implementation.
- **Local Entities:** Municipal entities and public institutions in the pilot cities.
- **Technical Partners:** Organizations specializing in developing software and managing sensor hardware.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Data Stewards:** A technical team that manages the architecture of the system to ensure continuous and accurate data flow.
- **Analysts:** Municipality employees trained to interpret dashboard data and convert the data into actions for urban planning decisions.
- **Data Protection Officer (DPO):** An individual responsible for ensuring that all data collected from citizens is compliant with GDPR.

Processes

- **Data Management Plan:** A formal plan to ensure that data is collected and shared in a manner that ensures it is Findable, Accessible, and Reusable (FAIR principles).
- **Interoperability Protocols:** Standard APIs to allow for seamless communication between the platform and existing city systems to avoid vendor lock-in.
- **Maintenance Routine:** Scheduled process to check the physical sensor network to prevent data gaps

Other requisites

- **Cloud infrastructure:** Scalable hosting (for example: AWS or equivalent on premises solutions) that can handle large amounts of data processing and storage.
- **IoT network:** Deployed network of sensors (for example: environmental and presence sensors) that communicates with standard protocols.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 9 - the technology has been used in an operational environment
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 7 - the solution is currently being refined and tested in a relevant environment with relevant stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Safety, and Spatial Well-being.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 7.1 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

2 - B4B tailored inclusive Business training

Solution developed by the IN-HABIT consortium partners

Value Proposition

An entrepreneurial training model adaptable to local circumstances for people who have historically been excluded from mainstream business support, including women and under-represented groups. The business model incorporates both practical business learning and confidence building, mentoring, and community support and can be delivered in formats that are responsive to local realities (i.e., in-person, online, hybrid). The model addresses barriers to entry, such as limited digital skills, lack of devices, time constraints, and limited access to networks so that participants can move from an idea to an action and connect into their local ecosystems.

Key Activities

- Accessibility & inclusivity of delivery: low-barrier communication (ex. WhatsApp voice notes), flexible scheduling, practical learning-by-doing.
- Curriculum localization: content reflecting local context, literacy levels and levels of preparedness of participants (e.g. language, examples, and pace).
- Mentorship & Coaching: one-on-one and small group support for building confidence, establishing structure, and creating accountability.
- Integration into Local Ecosystem: connections to local partners, services, and opportunities (potential customers, potential mentors, potential business support).
- Continuous Improvement: feedback mechanisms and light monitoring to improve the next cohort.

Cost Structure

- People: Trainers/Facilitators, Mentors, Outreach/Community Engagement, Coordination.
- Delivery: Venues, Materials, Translation/Adaptation, Participant Support Measures (as necessary).
- Tools: Simple communication and basic data tracking to monitor.

Revenue Streams

- Revenue streams include Product/Service Sales; Grants; Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR); Donations.

Partnerships

- Community Organizations/NGO's: Access, Trust-Building, Recruitment, On-The-Ground-Support.
- Municipalities/Public Agencies: Funding, Legitimacy, Inclusion & Employment Pathways.
- Educational Institutions: Co-Management Support, Venues, Training Expertise, Evaluation.
- Private Sector/COR Partners: Mentoring, Sponsorship, Equipment, Micro-Support.
- Mentorship Networks: Business Expertise and Follow-Up Support.

Replication prerequisites

People

- Community Activators (Trusted Local Connectors)
- Facilitators Trained in Inclusive Delivery
- Local Mentors/Coaches.

Processes

- Inclusive Recruitment via Grassroots Networks.
- Flexible Delivery Options (In-Person/Online/Hybrid) Based on Digital Readiness.
- Locally Relevant Materials (Language + Cultural Fit).
- Basic Post-Training Follow-Up.

Other requisites

- Options for Basic Digital Access (Devices/Access to Devices via Community).
- Adapted/Translated Curriculum and Templates.

Additional assessment indicators

- Technology Readiness Level: 0 - Non-Technological Solution (TRL Not Applicable).
- Societal Readiness Level: 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders.
- Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-Dimensions: Employment; Financial Situation; Equality; Social Inclusion.

For additional information regarding mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please see Chapters 6 and 11 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW."

Value Proposition

The Immersive Training Experience (ITE) is a serious game designed to help adults with Down's syndrome to train as hosts for conferences and events. This digital tool simulates real-life tasks, such as reception duties, catering and seating, helping users to practise routines, improve their memory and build their confidence. By combining gameplay with guided practice, the programme prepares participants to apply their skills in real work settings, creating genuine employment opportunities under standard.

Key Activities

- **Content creation:** Designing engaging, realistic training scenarios based on actual event locations and city themes.
- **App maintenance:** Regularly updating the tablet application to ensure smooth performance.
- **User Support:** Conducting onboarding sessions to familiarise users with the app and the learning process.
- **Evaluation:** Using data analytics to measure the programme's effectiveness and impact.
- **Marketing:** Promoting the programme to employers to increase job placement opportunities.

Cost Structure

- **Content production:** Costs for scripting, designing hyper-realistic 3D environments and creating interactive elements, including avatars and voice-overs.
- **Development and maintenance:** Expenses for software coding, platform hosting, technical support and regular updates.
- **Personnel:** Salaries for project managers, developers and the university research team.
- **Tests:** Costs associated with testing the app with participants from Down's syndrome associations.
- **Operations:** Marketing campaigns, office overheads and administrative costs.

Revenue Streams

Potential Revenue Streams Include Licensing and Grants.

Partnerships

University Research Team: Provided academic expertise and co-authored the user manual.

Software Developer: A software company responsible for building and hosting the immersive platform.

Down Syndrome association: essential to enable the project, provide professional insight and coordinate pilot testing with members.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Psychologists/Social Workers:** To guide users through emotional aspects of training.
- **Corporate Partners:** HR departments in event companies committed to offering internships/jobs to graduates.
- **Tech Support:** IT personnel to manage updates and assist with hardware issues.

Process

- **'Easy Reading' Methodology:** Ensures Instructions Meet Cognitive Accessibility Standards.
- **Repetitive Learning:** Gamified Learning Process Uses Structured Repetition to Consolidate Skills.
- **Accompanied placement:** Protocol for Transitioning Participants From Virtual Training to Real-World Employment With On-Site Supervision.

Other requisites

- **Hardware:** Tablets with Sufficient RAM (4 GB+), Specific Processors (Snapdragon) to Run the Immersive Environment Smoothly.
- **High-Speed Internet:** ac

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level: 6** - indicating that the solution has been validated through pilot testing in a relevant environment.
- **Societal Readiness Level: 7** - indicating that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Employment; Job and Skill Satisfaction; Social Inclusion.

Value Proposition

This initiative empowers city residents, families and community groups to grow their own food using accessible home-growing kits and practical educational activities. By adapting farming tools for small urban spaces, it reduces barriers to entry and strengthens ecological awareness, food literacy and personal well-being. The core offering combines:

- **Practical tools:** DIY kits designed for growing food in limited indoor or outdoor spaces.
- **Educational guidance:** Expert instruction delivered through workshops and learning materials.
- **Collective learning:** Experiences that foster social cohesion and shared responsibility for sustainability.

Key Activities

- **Product development:** Designing and producing DIY gardening kits that are suitable for small urban spaces and are made from sustainable materials.
- **Education:** Creating educational content on food cultivation and ecology and delivering workshops for schools and families.
- **Operations:** Managing the sourcing of materials, logistics and distribution of kits.
- **Outreach:** Promoting the initiative through community events, markets and digital channels.
- **Sales coordination:** Managing direct sales (B2C) and educational service contracts (B2B).

Cost Structure

- **Development:** Costs for designing prototypes, creating educational materials and planning workshops.
- **Production:** Expenses for purchasing sustainable materials and assembling the kits.
- **Operations:** Logistics, distribution and personnel costs for workshop facilitators.
- **Marketing:** Initial outreach and communication campaigns.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through Business-to-Consumer (B2C) sales of gardening kits and Business-to-Business (B2B) educational service contracts with municipalities and schools.

Partnerships

- **Educational institutions:** Schools and colleges that implement the workshops.
- **Public bodies:** Municipalities and cultural centres that commission educational activities.
- **Community groups:** NGOs and local organisations working with families and disadvantaged groups.
- **Sustainability networks:** Community gardens and environmental educators who contribute content and support.

Replication prerequisites

- Availability of small-scale urban spaces suitable for home growing.
- Access to basic sustainable materials and simple production capacities.
- Educational partners willing to integrate food literacy into their programmes.
- Municipal or institutional support for community-based learning activities.
- Demand for hands-on sustainability education among urban populations.
- Capacity to adapt kits and pedagogy to local climate and cultural contexts.
- Moderate initial funding for product development and outreach.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 2 - indicating that the solution is a technology concept.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** The solution did not explicitly target this.

Value Proposition

This initiative revitalises underused rural buildings by converting them into hybrid co-living and co-working spaces. It caters for remote workers, creative professionals, and others seeking a slower pace of life, connection to nature, and meaningful social interaction. By combining flexible accommodation with professional workspaces and wellbeing activities, the project fosters community engagement and contributes to the regeneration of rural areas.

Key Activities

- **Property development:** renovating and adapting rural properties for reuse.
- **Operations:** Managing accommodation, workspaces and on-site guest services.
- **Experience design:** organising cultural, wellbeing and community events, as well as local nature and food experiences.
- **Community building:** Facilitating connections between residents, local stakeholders and neighbours.
- **Marketing:** Promoting the spaces through digital nomad platforms and coordinating with tourism networks.

Cost Structure

- **Capital and setup:** Costs for property acquisition (or leasing), renovation, furnishing and installing high-speed internet infrastructure.
- **Operations:** Ongoing expenses for maintenance, utilities and platform fees.
- **Personnel:** Salaries for staff managing guest services and community facilitation.
- **Marketing:** Budget for branding, market entry and event delivery.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through medium-term accommodation rentals and workspace rentals. Additional revenue streams include the sale of event tickets and local experience packages.

Partnerships

- **Public bodies:** Rural municipalities and regional regeneration agencies.
- **Local economy:** farmers, artisans and service providers offering authentic local products and experiences.
- **Networks:** Regional tourism boards and digital nomad platforms.
- **Facilitators:** Experts in culture and wellbeing who deliver on-site programming.

Replication prerequisites

- **Infrastructure:** Access to suitable rural properties with permission for adaptive reuse.
- **Connectivity:** Reliable high-speed internet is essential for remote working.
- **Local ecosystem:** A community capable of providing authentic local experiences (food, nature, culture).
- **Capital and management:** Funding for renovation and the capacity to manage hospitality and community dynamics.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 2 - indicating that the solution is a technology concept.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 5 - indicating that the solution has been validated by relevant stakeholders in the area.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Housing; Spatial Well-being.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.2 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This multifunctional urban marketplace transforms public spaces into accessible, safe and vibrant community health and wellbeing hubs. It promotes healthy lifestyles by improving access to nutritious food and supporting sustainable mobility through infrastructure such as bicycle facilities. Beyond commerce, the marketplace acts as a social hub, hosting cultural events and 'Co-creation Cuisine' initiatives to foster intergenerational connections and reduce social isolation. It also promotes economic inclusion by supporting local producers and creating training and employment opportunities for disadvantaged groups.

Key Activities

- **Infrastructure development:** Renovating market squares and public spaces, installing accessibility features such as ramps and lifts, and creating facilities like community kitchens and waste management 'eco-islands'.
- **Programme implementation:** Involves organising cultural, social and educational events, including culinary workshops and youth festivals, to promote healthy eating and sustainability.
- **Community building:** mapping local stakeholders, training community activators and facilitating workshops to build trust and local networks.
- **Economic development:** Offering incubation programmes, training and mentoring to social entrepreneurs.

Cost Structure

- **Capital investment:** Costs allocated to the construction and renovation of physical spaces, including kitchens, eco-islands and digital purchasing systems.
- **Operational expenses:** Include salaries for cultural coordinators and staff, event materials, and marketing campaigns.
- **Maintenance:** Ongoing funds are required to maintain the facilities and ensure long-term sustainability.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue can be generated through activities such as renting out spaces, charging for workshops or pop-up restaurants, and catering.

Partnerships

- **Lead partners:** collaborations between public authorities, research institutions and social enterprises.
- **Local stakeholders:** A broad network including residents, NGOs, farmers, local businesses, schools, artists and neighbourhood associations.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Agile management team:** A professional team capable of balancing commercial viability with the project's social mission.
- **Community Connectors:** Staff dedicated to curating cultural content and engaging with neighbourhood associations to ensure the market serves the local community, not just tourists.
- **Pro-sustainability vendors:** Traders willing to adopt waste reduction practices and participate in food donation schemes.

Processes

- **Flexible lease model:** Long-term agreements, which grant operators autonomy in exchange for capital investment and social deliverables.
- **Cross-subsidisation:** A financial model where revenue from commercial stalls subsidises community areas such as kitchens and educational spaces.
- **Waste minimisation:** strict protocols for waste separation and utilisation of the 'Eco-Island' system.

Other requisites

- **Multifunctional zoning:** Spaces designed for mixed use, combining sales areas with zones for co-creation, events and education.
- **Accessibility upgrades:** Essential installations such as lifts and ramps to make the space inclusive for the elderly and people with disabilities.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 5 - indicating that the solution is being validated in a relevant environment (only the 'Co-creation kitchen' uses technology).
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 7 - indicating that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Social cohesion; Cultural participation; Financial situation.

Value Proposition

This digital marketplace connects small-scale rural food producers directly with urban consumers who want fresh, healthy and traceable food. By curating seasonal products and facilitating direct delivery, the platform shortens supply chains, improves transparency and strengthens local food systems.

The value proposition combines:

- **Convenience:** easy access to locally produced, seasonal food.
- **Trust:** full transparency regarding food origins and production methods.
- **Sustainability:** Eco-conscious consumption through reduced food waste and optimised logistics.

Key Activities

- **Digital Marketplace:** Operating a platform that links rural producers with urban buyers.
- **Supply chain management:** Curating seasonal offerings and managing direct-to-consumer delivery to support a resilient local food system.

Cost Structure

- **Development:** Costs for platform design, technical development and setting up logistics systems.
- **Operations:** Expenses for IT maintenance, logistics partnerships (including the cold chain), and personnel for customer support and producer relations.
- **Marketing and Sales:** Budget for community engagement, marketing campaigns and transaction fees.
- **Onboarding:** Costs associated with bringing new producers onto the platform and ensuring quality control.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue can be generated through commission-based sales on transactions, premium subscriptions for consumers, and the sale of curated seasonal boxes.

Partnerships

- **Producers:** Small-scale farmers and artisanal food producers.
- **Logistics providers:** Local partners who manage home deliveries and collection points.
- **Community:** Conscious consumer groups, food NGOs and workplace or neighbourhood hubs acting as collection points.
- **Public sector:** Municipal actors working on food policy and urban sustainability.

Replication prerequisites

- **Supply and demand:** a sufficient number of local producers willing to sell directly, coupled with urban consumer demand for transparent, seasonal food.
- **Infrastructure:** A robust digital platform for e-commerce and subscriptions, supported by reliable logistics and cold chain solutions.
- **Management:** The capacity to manage seasonal variability and curate product lines.
- **Policy alignment:** Support from local food strategies or sustainability policies.
- **Investment:** Moderate initial funding for technology and operational setup.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment and in co-operation with relevant stakeholders to gain initial feedback on potential impact.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** Level: 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Social cohesion; Financial situation; Employment; Social inclusion

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.5 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This business offers a clean, herbal, tea-based energy drink designed for health-conscious consumers. It provides sustained energy, focus and hydration, and avoids the sugar, artificial ingredients and 'crashes' associated with conventional energy drinks. Combining functional wellness with environmental responsibility, the product targets two main groups:

- B2C consumers: individuals seeking a daily ritual that supports mental clarity and well-being.
- B2B partners: Yoga studios, wellness centres and retreats that want to offer their clients a product that aligns with their values.

Key Activities

- **Production:** Formulating and manufacturing a herbal, tea-based functional beverage.
- **Distribution:** Managing a subscription-based model for regular customers and handling logistics for B2B orders.
- **Marketing:** Positioning the brand for wellness-oriented consumers through digital content and partnerships.
- **Sales:** Acquiring customers via online channels and maintaining relationships with wellness studios and retreats.
- **Sustainability:** Implementing environmental initiatives such as planting a tree for every pack sold and transitioning to zero-waste packaging.

Cost Structure

- **Production:** Procurement of raw ingredients, manufacturing and packaging.
- **Operations:** Logistics, distribution and subscription fulfilment.
- **Marketing:** Costs for paid advertising, content creation and influencer collaborations.
- **Personnel:** Salaries for the growing team.
- **Sustainability:** Funding for environmental impact initiatives.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through direct product sales, recurring subscription models, and limited-edition campaigns.

Partnerships

- **Wellness networks:** yoga studios, teachers and retreat centres that act as distribution channels and brand ambassadors.
- **Operational partners:** Logistics and production providers who ensure a reliable supply and delivery service.
- **Promotional partners:** influencers and marketers who support brand growth.
- **Investors:** Strategic backers who share the brand's vision for wellness and sustainability.

Replication prerequisites

- **Market demand:** A sufficient segment of health-conscious consumers looking for functional beverages.
- **Infrastructure:** Access to reliable production facilities and logistics for subscription delivery.
- **Brand positioning:** A strong identity linked to wellness and environmental values.
- **Compliance:** Compliance with food and beverage regulations in target markets.
- **Partnerships:** Established connections with local wellness ecosystems (e.g. corporate wellness programmes and gyms).
- **Commitment:** Financial resources for market entry and dedication to impact measures such as reforestation.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level: 9** - indicating that the solution was proven in an operational environment.
- **Societal Readiness Level: 9** - indicating that the solution was proven in a relevant environment.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** The solution did not explicitly target this.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.6 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

The HADUP Centre offers specialised consulting services designed to integrate human-animal bonds into urban planning. It provides bespoke policy frameworks, strategies and specialised training to help cities create inclusive, human-centred spaces. By combining evidence-based planning with thought leadership, the Centre establishes itself as a trusted expert in improving urban health and wellbeing through human-animal policies.

Key Activities

- **Specialised research:** Conducting research on human-animal bonds and inclusive health and wellbeing (IHW) using participatory action research (PAR).
- **Policy co-design:** Facilitating workshops where stakeholders collaborate to design effective policies.
- **Training:** Delivering targeted sessions to help officials implement these policies successfully.
- **Project management:** Managing lean pilot projects using agile coordination methods.
- **Thought leadership:** Building authority in the field through advocacy and publications.

Cost Structure

- **Personnel:** Salaries for expert consultants and staff.
- **Operations:** Costs for office space (physical or virtual), software and travel.
- **Research:** Funding for targeted studies to maintain expert status.
- **Networking:** expenses for attending conferences and producing thought leadership content.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through consulting fees for policy design and implementation, training fees for capacity building, and research fees for impact assessments. Additionally, funding is derived from EU grants for pilot projects.

Partnerships

- **Universities:** Provide academic rigour, research and veterinary/behavioural expertise.
- **Municipalities:** Can act as pilot cities and reference cases for policy implementation.
- **Urban planning associations:** Facilitate outreach and industry connections.
- **NGOs and community groups:** offer on-the-ground insights and support implementation.
- **Funders:** Organisations providing financial backing.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Pet Policy Manager:** A professional with cross-cutting skills in urban planning, ethology and public administration,
- **Cross-Departmental Board:** A working group of councillors from Social Services, Environment and Urban Planning to break down administrative silos.
- **Scientific advisors:** collaboration with veterinary or ethology experts to ensure policies are evidence-based.

Processes

- **Participatory council:** A formal council where stakeholders (vets, pet owners and non-owners) jointly design conflict prevention rules.
- **Regulatory alignment:** updating local bylaws to allow animals in public offices, nursing homes and on public transport.

Other requisites

- **Animal-Nature Based Solutions (A-NBS):** Recognising facilities such as dog parks ('Animal Lines') as essential social infrastructure rather than just waste areas.
- **Data mapping:** Using GIS to map pet density and needs in order to inform infrastructure planning.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 0 - indicating that the solution is not developing a technological innovation.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** Level: 7 - indicating that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Spatial Well-being; Equality; Social inclusion.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 9.1 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This initiative uses animal-assisted interventions (AAIs) as a natural, stigma-free way of supporting underserved individuals, particularly the elderly in residential care. By introducing animal-nature-based solutions (A-NBS), it offers beneficiaries significant health and wellbeing improvements:

- **Emotional wellbeing:** Companionship with animals reduces loneliness, alleviates depression and buffers against stress.
- **Cognitive stimulation:** Activities encourage communication, engagement, and memory recall (e.g. remembering pets or names).
- **Physical activity:** Interaction involves gentle movement, such as petting, brushing, or playing.
- **Social connection:** Shared time and spaces foster bonding and a renewed sense of belonging.

Key Activities.

- **Session delivery:** Designing and delivering tailored intervention plans based on the specific needs of residents and nursing homes.
- **Partnership management:** Building relationships with care homes, local authorities and stakeholders to increase reach and integration.
- **Animal welfare:** Providing rigorous, continuous training and health management for therapy animals to ensure safety and ethical treatment.
- **Staff development:** Ensuring continuous professional training and certification for therapists and handlers.

Cost Structure

- **Personnel:** Salaries for licensed therapists, coordinators and administrative staff.
- **Animal care:** expenses for veterinary checks, vaccinations, food, grooming and specialised insurance.
- **Operations:** Costs for transport, session equipment, office supplies and liability insurance.
- **Training:** Budget for the ongoing development of both human staff and therapy animals.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through public funding (primary), derived from municipal, national, and regional health and social care budgets. This is complemented by emerging public service contracts with local authorities and significant EU and philanthropic grants focused on social innovation and ageing. Additional income streams include direct revenue from user fees for enhanced services, donations via corporate CSR and community fundraising, and partnership contributions in the form of in-kind support from universities and NGOs.

Partnerships

- **Care homes** are essential partners that provide access to beneficiaries and integrate sessions into daily routines.
- **Public authorities**, such as municipalities and health bodies, provide funding, legitimacy and regulatory support.
- **Universities are academic centres** that offer research support, evaluation methodologies and student internships.
- **Veterinary services** are crucial for monitoring the health and welfare of therapy animals.
- **Organisations (NGOs)** that assist with outreach, volunteer recruitment, and advocacy.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Certified professionals:** Handlers and therapists who are trained in accordance with national guidelines.
- **Veterinarians:** Experts who monitor animal welfare (e.g. stress levels) to prevent exploitation.

Processes

- **Public procurement:** Administrative procedures for tendering services to NGOs, ensuring quality and compliance.
- **Rigorous protocols:** standardised session plans tailored to patients with dementia or mobility issues.
- **Informed consent:** Ethical procedures for obtaining permission from participants or their guardians.

Other requisites

- **Suitable animals:** specially selected and trained animals that have passed behavioural assessments.
- **Insurance:** Specific liability cover for animal-related incidents within health facilities.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 0 - indicating that the solution is not developing a technological innovation.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** Level: 7 - indicating that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Social inclusion; Social cohesion

Value Proposition

This service supports individuals who are temporarily underserved by helping them with their pet care needs. By providing support during challenging periods, it alleviates anxiety, prevents social isolation and safeguards the physical and mental well-being of both owners and their pets. The service offers three core levels of support:

- **Domestic services:** in-home care (feeding, cleaning and grooming) and delivery of essential supplies.
- **Assisted outdoor services:** accompanying the owner to transport the pet to the vet or walking the dog.
- **Independent outdoor services:** walking the dog or transporting the pet to appointments on the owner's behalf.

Key Activities

- **Service provision:** Delivering daily care (feeding, administering medication), managing supply procurement and conducting walks or transport.
- **Client onboarding:** Assessing the vulnerability of new clients to understand the specific health and safety needs of both human and pet.
- **Staffing:** recruiting and training compassionate caregivers in pet first aid, emergency procedures and client sensitivity.
- **Partnership building:** Collaborating with local councils, social services and healthcare providers to secure referrals and funding.
- **Network engagement:** Building relationships with local vets for referrals and pet stores for potential discounts.

Cost Structure

- **Personnel:** Salaries for pet caregivers, drivers, client managers and administrative staff.
- **Logistics:** Costs for purchasing or leasing vehicles, fuel, insurance and maintenance.
- **Training:** Ongoing professional development for staff in pet care and supporting underserved populations.
- **Marketing:** Expenses for community outreach and digital advertising to reach those in need.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through a fixed price table. There is also the potential for a membership/subscription model. This could be supplemented by forming partnerships with private urban developers on large-scale integrated projects.

Partnerships

- **Municipalities:** The primary customers and co-developers who serve as pilot sites for the service.
- **Social and health services:** Government departments that provide referrals and align the service with city-wide wellbeing goals.
- **Healthcare providers:** Hospitals and home care agencies that refer patients during recovery or incapacitation.
- **Charities:** Local groups that help connect the service with communities of people on low incomes, with disabilities, or who are elderly.
- **Lead partners:** Collaborations between research institutions, social enterprises and public authorities.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Vulnerability assessors:** Social workers or administrative staff who are qualified to identify and validate beneficiaries.
- **Logistics Network:** A coordinated team of staff or volunteers capable of providing walking, fostering and transport services.

Processes

- **Emergency protocol:** A system for rapidly deploying support when a beneficiary is facing an immediate crisis.
- **Formal agreements:** Legal frameworks between the municipality and NGOs to authorise service provision.
- **Management interface:** A simple platform or phone line for booking services and coordinating volunteers.

Infrastructure

- **Transport:** Access to pet-friendly vehicles suitable for veterinary visits and safe transportation.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 0 - indicating that the solution is not developing a technological innovation.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** Level: 7 - indicating that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Financial situation; Security.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 9.3 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This digital platform streamlines pet care management and enhances access to animal health services. It addresses the needs of two key groups:

- **Pet owners:** Saves time and reduces stress by providing personalised reminders, document storage and direct access to service providers.
- **Professionals (vets and groomers):** Can use it to showcase their services, manage bookings and communicate with clients, solving the sector's lack of online visibility.

Key Activities

- **Platform development:** Building and maintaining a mobile application for iOS and Android.
- **User management:** Managing features such as personalised notifications, document storage and file sharing.
- **Service aggregation:** Continuously updating the database of service providers.
- **Booking system:** Facilitating direct contact, appointment scheduling and client management tools for professionals.
- **Promotion:** Marketing the platform through online and offline channels.
- **Expansion:** Gradually integrating additional services, such as pet sitting and training.

Cost Structure

- **Development:** Costs for software engineering, legal compliance and registration.
- **Operations:** Ongoing platform maintenance, updates and infrastructure expenses.
- **Growth:** Budget for marketing campaigns and scaling the team.
- **Innovation:** Investment in advanced booking and management tools.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through a freemium approach: basic features are provided to owners free of charge, while professionals pay monthly subscription fees for premium features and visibility.

Partnerships

- **Service providers:** Veterinary clinics, groomers and trainers registered on the platform.
- **Business partners:** Strategic allies supporting platform growth and service expansion.
- **Promotional partners:** agencies and networks assisting with communication.
- **Institutions:** Public or sectoral bodies involved in animal welfare ecosystems.

Replication prerequisites

- **Market scale:** A critical mass of active pet owners and service providers.
- **Technology:** Robust mobile infrastructure that is fully compliant with data protection regulations.
- **Engagement:** Service providers willing to maintain updated online profiles.
- **Financials:** Investment capacity for marketing and a market ready for subscription-based models.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 5 - indicating that the solution has been validated in a relevant environment.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 5 - indicating that the solution has been validated by relevant Stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** The solution did not explicitly target this.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.3 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This initiative provides animal-assisted interventions (AAIs) for children, adults and older people who are physically or psychologically underserved. Moving away from clinical, medicalised settings, the programme uses structured interaction with animals and nature to boost motivation, engagement, autonomy and social skills. The core value lies in three pillars:

- **Environment:** A welcoming, non-institutional space designed specifically for underserved users.
- **Expertise:** Highly trained professionals who receive continuous updates in their field.
- **Ethics:** High standards of animal welfare, ensuring that animals are respected participants **rather** than tools.

Key Activities

- **Service delivery:** Providing animal-assisted activities (AAA), education (AAE) and therapy (AAT).
- **Pathway co-design:** Collaborating with social cooperatives and care managers to create personalised intervention plans.
- **Team coordination:** Managing a diverse team of educators, psychologists, ethologists, musicians, veterinarians and certified handlers.
- **Animal care:** Daily management and welfare checks for all therapy animals.
- **Evaluation:** Monitoring outcomes through interviews, psychological tests and progress tracking.

Cost Structure

- **Infrastructure:** Costs for property acquisition (or leasing), renovation, furnishing and maintenance.
- **Operations:** Expenses for utilities, high-speed internet and platform fees.
- **Personnel:** Salaries for staff, including guest services and community facilitators.
- **Programming:** Budget for event delivery, marketing, branding and partnership coordination.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through a mixed funding strategy. This revenue comes from public service contracts with municipalities and health agencies, as well as private support from foundations and philanthropic organisations.

Partnerships

- **Public authorities:** Rural municipalities that support regeneration and the activation of local spaces.
- **Tourism networks:** Regional boards and local tourism groups.
- **Local Economy:** Producers, artisans and service providers who contribute to the local economy.
- **Digital platforms:** Networks for digital nomads and co-working spaces.
- **Facilitators:** Experts in culture and wellbeing who assist with programming.

Replication prerequisites

- **Environment:** A suitable natural setting adapted for underserved users.
- **Expertise:** Access to certified professionals and veterinary support.
- **Standards:** Strong ethical guidelines and animal welfare protocols.
- **Operations:** Capacity to manage long-term personalised pathways and monitor outcomes.
- **Sustainability:** Financial stability to cover costs and ensure surplus.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 1 - indicating that the Basic principles are observed and reported.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 9 - indicating that the solution was proven in a relevant environment.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Social inclusion; Social cohesion.

Value Proposition

This community bike-sharing service provides an affordable and sustainable transport solution that encourages an active lifestyle. By using bicycles refurbished from spare parts and offering seasonal rentals, the service fosters a circular economy. It uniquely involves the community in co-designing the service and public spaces, thereby enhancing urban living, safety and cleanliness. A dedicated repair workshop encourages users to maintain the bikes, fostering a sense of ownership. The initiative also generates economic value by creating opportunities for social entrepreneurship, training, and employment.

Key Activities

- **Operations:** Managing bike rentals and the repair workshop.
- **Co-design:** collaborating with locals to plan cycle routes and integrate them into public spaces.
- **Volunteering:** Organising activities such as bike repairs, litter collection, planting and road maintenance.
- **Education and feedback:** running thematic workshops (e.g. bike safety) and conducting annual surveys to gather improvement ideas.

Cost Structure

- **Personnel:** Salaries for staff managing operations, maintenance and community coordination.
- **Materials:** Costs for purchasing and maintaining refurbished bikes and spare parts (often reduced by partnering with recycling firms).
- **Operations:** Expenses for warehousing, venue hire, insurance, permits and administration.
- **Events and training:** Budget for organising workshops and public events, and for purchasing supplies.
- **Marketing:** Costs for media documentation, campaigns and user engagement.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through tiered rental fees (for monthly or six-month periods) and usage-based charges. Different pricing tables apply at various times of the year. Additional funding can be secured through municipal budget allocations for urban development, public spaces and social services.

Partnerships

- **Implementation partner:** the organisation responsible for managing the service and community engagement.
- **Supply chain:** suppliers of new and used bicycle parts, payment providers and insurance companies.
- **Public sector:** local government and institutions that provide site access, permits and urban planning expertise.
- **Academia:** Universities that support research and evaluate the project's social impact.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Community Manager:** A trusted local leader (e.g. from a cultural centre) who oversees the system.
- **Volunteer mechanics:** Local youth or DIY enthusiasts who are trained to repair and maintain the fleet.

Processes

- **Trust-based lending:** a low-barrier rental system that relies on community ownership rather than expensive automated docking stations.
- **Circular sourcing:** protocols for acquiring and refurbishing abandoned or donated bicycles.

Other requisites

- **Secure depot:** A physical space (e.g. a shipping container) within a safe community hub for storage and repairs.
- **Cycling paths:** Basic, safe infrastructure to enable riders to use the service effectively.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 0 - indicating that the solution is not developing a technological innovation.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Spatial Well-being; Financial situation; Safety

Value Proposition

This initiative establishes cyclist-friendly rest and refreshment hubs along semi-rural cycling routes. Designed for families, individuals and informal groups, the hubs offer food and drink, bike rental, basic servicing and social spaces. By filling the infrastructure gap for longer, family-friendly trips, the hubs promote physical wellbeing alongside convenience and comfort. They also promote local identity by featuring regional products in their tourism offerings.

Key Activities

- **Operations:** Managing self-service 'Freshbox' snack units, bike rentals, and basic repair services.
- **Supply chain:** Coordinating with local suppliers for food and beverages.
- **Marketing:** Promoting the hubs via digital channels, social media and cycling maps (points of interest).
- **Collaboration:** Working with municipalities and tourism bodies to increase visibility and host events.

Cost Structure

- **Infrastructure:** Installation of Freshbox units, bike rental equipment and small-scale physical structures.
- **Stock and maintenance:** Purchasing food and beverage inventory and servicing bicycles.
- **Personnel:** Wages for technical and operational staff.
- **Overheads:** Utilities, marketing campaigns and initial platform listing fees.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through food and beverage sales, seasonal events, and partnerships with local producers.

Partnerships

- **Local suppliers:** Providers of regional food and drink, prioritising local products.
- **Public sector:** Municipalities and tourism offices that assist with site placement and promotion.
- **Digital platforms:** Mapping services and cycling apps that integrate the hubs as points of interest.
- **Ecosystem partners:** Strategic allies that support community engagement and visibility.

Replication prerequisites

- **Location:** Existing or emerging cycling routes with recreational traffic.
- **Support:** Municipal backing for permits and site placement.
- **Supply:** Local producers willing to supply food and beverages.
- **Investment:** Moderate upfront capital for modular infrastructure.
- **Demand:** Sufficient seasonal traffic to support onsite sales.
- **Management:** Capacity for basic operations and maintenance.
- **Strategy:** Alignment with regional goals for active mobility, rural tourism and wellbeing.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 2 - indicating that the solution is a technology concept.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Leisure & Free Time

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.7 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This initiative transforms unused local sheep's wool into handcrafted clothing, accessories and homeware. It combines traditional textile techniques with contemporary, eco-conscious design. By collaborating with local farmers and processors, the project restores regional wool value chains and prevents waste and overproduction.

The value proposition is based on:

- **Sustainable production:** made-to-order and small-batch items to avoid surplus stock.
- **Transparency:** Full visibility of material origins and production methods.
- **Durability:** Timeless products designed for long-term use.
- **Identity:** Fashion that integrates cultural storytelling and regional heritage.

Key Activities

- **Sourcing:** Procuring raw wool from local farmers and regional suppliers.
- **Production:** Coordinating yarn preparation with local processors and overseeing artisanal knitting.
- **Design:** developing products, including custom pieces and limited editions.
- **Sales:** managing direct sales via social media, pre-orders, pop-up markets and select stores.
- **Education:** Organising workshops for schools and the public.
- **Communication:** Promoting sustainability and storytelling through digital channels.

Cost Structure

- **Production:** Costs for raw materials (e.g. wool and yarn), prototyping, and payments to artisans and processors.
- **Operations:** Logistics, packaging and digital infrastructure (branding and web).
- **Services:** Fees for outsourced professionals (design, photography, marketing).
- **Marketing:** expenses for events, pop-ups and customer acquisition campaigns.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through direct sales of woollen products, limited-edition collections, and creative partnerships. Workshops also contribute to the revenue mix.

Partnerships

- **Supply chain:** Local sheep farmers and regional wool processors.
- **Creatives:** Designers, textile specialists, photographers and storytellers.
- **Retail and education:** Concept stores, artisan shops and schools hosting workshops.
- **Networks:** Creative and environmental organisations that support visibility and funding.

Replication prerequisites

- **Resources:** Availability of underutilised natural fibres (e.g. wool and flax).
- **Skills:** Access to skilled artisans or textile expertise.
- **Collaboration:** Farmers willing to participate in short supply chains.
- **Facilities:** Access to small-scale production or processing partners.
- **Market:** Demand for sustainable, locally made products.
- **Operations:** Capacity for storytelling and direct-to-consumer sales.
- **Strategy:** Alignment with circular economy and cultural heritage goals.
- **Investment:** Low to moderate start-up capital focused on materials and market entry.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 1 - indicating that the Basic principles are observed and reported.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 9 - indicating that the solution was proven in a relevant environment.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Employment; Job and skill satisfaction; Cultural participation.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.8 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".